

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO DIVERSIFY AND IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. The complex nature of tourism, its strong cross-sectoral linkages and regional dimension make innovation difficult. The emergence of smart specialization focused on regional diversification across sectors offers a huge and so far untapped potential for innovative tourism policy development within this new agenda. The article discusses innovative ways to diversify and improve the quality of tourist services in Uzbekistan.

Keywords. Tourism, tourist services, innovation, diversification of tourist services, tourist market.

Introduction. Tourism policies have been recognized to support employment and investment, taxes, foreign exchange, rapid return of income, economic diversification at local, regional and national levels and, more recently, the creation of cross-sectoral linkages. Tourism, like agriculture, is seen as an alternative to the decline in traditional industries, particularly in backward or remote areas where regional policy promotes diversification strategies.

The tourist market is a place where socio-economic relations between producers and consumers take place, combining demand and supply to ensure the process of selling tourist products. In it, the process of turning tourist services into money takes place.

Each producer and consumer of a tourism product will have their own

economic interests, which may not be compatible with each other.

If the interests of the parties match, the sale of the tourist product will take place.

The market is a unique means of harmonizing the interests of production and consumption. The main place in it is occupied by the buyer (client). The seller's obligation is to meet the needs of his customers.

The tourist market is a complex category, because its products are often sold not directly, but through intermediaries (business entities - tour operators - travel agents).

In a broad sense, the tourist market means a place where tourist products (tourist tours, individual goods or services) are sold.

It should be taken into account that tourist service transactions are not always carried out in the same place (for example, in a hotel or tour operator). The tourist market is not limited to a specific place or geographical area, therefore, the sale of tourist products can be carried out by telex, telegram, fax, phone call, cash book, rather than the direct participation of its seller and buyer.

The following conditions must be observed in the market: free competition - all market participants try to achieve their goals (selling their products at maximum profit or purchasing goods at minimum cost); the existence of basic regulations on the quality and safety of the tourist product; consumer choice.

The modern tourist market performs the following specific functions: 1. The function of selling the value and consumption value of the tourist product. This represents the movement of value and is reflected in the monetization of the tourist product. As a result of this, a normal state of social reproduction is ensured, funds (money) for the development of tourism appear and accumulate. 2. The function of organizing the process of delivering the tourist product to the consumer (tourist). It is carried out through travel agents and tour operators. By spending money on tourism, the tourist satisfies his material and spiritual needs.

Accordingly, the tourist market provides an opportunity to restore and reproduce the basic productive forces of society. 3. The function of providing financial resources for the material levers of product reproduction. This means that the tourist product is converted into money in the market and a financial base is created for the next production. Product movement ends.

The tourist market has its own characteristics and includes the following: 1. Tourist services are an intangible activity. In this case, the reliability of the product, guarantee of the promised quality level, accurate information about the consumption characteristics of the type occupy an important place. This depends on the confidence of customers in the company and its stability in the market. 2. There should not be a big gap between the time of purchasing the tourist product and its consumption, therefore, the accuracy and reliability of the channels of moving the tourist product and the responsibility of the enterprise for the sold product are important. 3. Touristic demand is affected by seasonal fluctuations and irregularity of the tourist flow. The reduction of these negative situations can be achieved through the method of price differentiation for service elements by seasons, as well as by reducing the capacity of transporting tourists. 4. The quality of the product will depend significantly on the exact performers. Therefore, the management within the tourist enterprise should always be developed.

In the tourist market there is a territorial fragmentation between the consumer and the producer. Therefore, it is important to establish operational relations with distant partners.

Like other markets, the tourist market operates according to the law of supply and demand.

Tourist demand is manifested in the need of the population for a tourist product, confirmed by the ability to pay. Tourist demand is reflected in a certain number of tourist excursion services, which can be purchased by the population at current prices.

Supply in accordance with the demand in the market: the tourist is guaranteed various district services necessary during the vacation and travel.

Supply is the ideal readiness and real possibilities of producers of goods (products) to deliver a certain number of these goods to the market.

The supply of tourist products depends on the availability of tourist products, the level of development of the tourist industry, and the size of tourist resources.

There is a close relationship between supply and demand: not only does demand guarantee supply, but supply in a sense influences demand. For example, the volume of the offer of tourist services increases when prices increase and decreases when prices decrease.

In the market, the tourist's funds are exchanged for tourist products. In a balanced exchange, on the one hand, the interests of the tourist product producer and consumer are satisfied, and on the other hand, conditions are created for the rapid development of the tourist industry.

The tourist market is characterized by capacity, that is, the ability to sell a certain amount of tourist products at the current prices and supply in a certain period of time (usually a year).

Market capacity depends on the population's ability to pay (demand), price level and description of tourist offer. Depending on the price level, the need for tourist products may decrease or, on the contrary, increase.

By knowing the market capacity and its changing trends, the tourist enterprise will be able to assess the prospects of this market for itself.

In the tourist market, there is a constant flow of money and the movement of the tourist product, that is, reproduction occurs.

Reproduction is a system of economic relations, within which services are transformed into money and vice versa. It shows the flow of tourism products, investments in the development of the tourism industry and income from tourism

activities to the budget.

Tourist reproduction is carried out according to the following scheme: 1. The tourist buys a ticket and pays money to the tourist enterprise. 2. As a result, the tourist satisfies his essential needs. 3. The tourist enterprise receives money for the sold tourist products, makes investments for the development of the tourist industry, produces or buys new types of tourist products. 4. The tourist enterprise pays taxes, various fees to the budget and wages to its employees.

A tourist enterprise should work stably in a constantly changing competitive environment. The elements of this environment are a number of markets that determine the situation of tourist products and influence the economy of the tourist enterprise. They include: labor market; financial market; investment market; tourist product market.

The labor market is the sphere of attraction of labor force and intelligence necessary for the development of tourist activity. The labor market provides an opportunity to develop the purchasing power of the population and accumulate the earned wages.

Financial market - influences personal savings, regulation of state credit policy, redistributes accumulated funds to consumer loans and investments.

The investment market is the purchase of assets called "long-term tangible goods" by enterprises (mainly real estate). The investment market develops depending on the interest rates on loans.

Discussion. By compensating for the declining contribution of other sectors, especially given its high stability compared to other sectors, tourism supports the GDP in times of economic crisis. This is especially the case in rural areas, where competitive advantages include a combination of natural and cultural values with unique attractions that can provide sustainable income to rural residents. Nevertheless, given that tourism is vulnerable due to its strong dependence on cultural and natural resources, its competitiveness depends on the

sustainable use of territorial resources. In addition, destination differentiation depends on the integration of cultural and natural resources into the tourism offer and their preservation over time.

The success of using tourism for sustainable development depends on the wise use of diversification and specialization policies. Taking into account that tourism markets are very delicate and risky, i.e. they are volatile, full of consumer quality uncertainties and constantly changing consumer lifestyles, tourism companies are forced to be innovative and diversify their goods and services. Thus, innovation and diversification in tourism are essential to achieve competitive advantage.

In many developed economies, tourism is becoming a knowledge-based activity with great potential for developing innovative strategies based on space and practices that depend on the human skills, natural and cultural resources available in specific places and regions. Yet tourism remains isolated from the broader literature on innovation systems and policies, and research on innovation policy remains limited. Tourist services worth 315 billion soums were provided in Uzbekistan in 9 months. According to the State Statistics Committee, in the 9th month of 2022, services of tourist agencies, tour operators, booking and other related services were provided in Uzbekistan worth 315.2 billion soums. The largest volume of these services was recorded in Tashkent city. The State Statistics Committee provided information on the volume of services of tourist agencies, tour operators, reservations and other related services in January-September 2022. It is known that in 9 months, tourist services worth 315.2 billion soums were provided in Uzbekistan. The volume of services of tourist agencies, tour operators, booking and other related services in the region is as follows: Republic of Karakalpakstan - 2.2 billion soums; Andijan - 1.8 billion soums; Bukhara - 10.7 billion soums; Jizzakh - 0.8 billion soums; Kashkadarya - 2.5 billion soums; Navoi - 3.0 billion soums; Namangan - 6.7 billion soums;

Samarkand - 20.7 billion soums; Surkhandarya - 1.2 billion soums; Syrdaryo - 1.0 billion soums; Tashkent - 6.8 billion soums; Fergana - 8.4 billion soums; Khorezm - 23.1 billion soums; Tashkent city - 226.3 billion soums.

Innovation processes are often supported by firms and regions to implement innovation policies aimed at diversification, including expansion into new markets or entry into new sectors. Therefore, specialization and diversification are relevant to tourism innovation policy studies and literature.

Innovation is the process of turning new ideas into marketable results and plays a crucial role in economic growth. Tourism innovations can comprise product, process, organizational-management and market innovations, as well as distribution innovations and institutional innovations specific to tourism. They often constitute smaller changes or improvements rather than entirely new products or new markets. New experimental packages of products and services at a defined regional level often constitute innovations developed through collaboration between tourism or non-tourism actors in the business, public and non-profit sectors.

So far, tourism innovation system policy has emphasized the cluster approach, which implies the role of complementary firms in facilitating intra-regional networking, cooperation and knowledge transfer. However, vague and failed cluster innovation policies have led to a more holistic but place-based approach in modern innovation policy, which is supported by the logic of regional innovation systems.

Regional innovation systems consist of a subsystem of knowledge production and dissemination, including research and development organizations, educational institutions, and technology transfer agencies, and a subsystem of knowledge application and exploitation, which includes companies and clusters located in the region. Subsystems are linked by intensive knowledge flows, resources and human capital, which are the basis for fundamental and systemic

innovation. Over the past three decades, different aspects of RIS have been emphasized in different time periods and places, and more recently a sector-based policy approach has emerged in the area of regional innovation.

There is an increasing focus on foreign aid and government intervention in RIS in tourism, where differentiated innovative policies that address regional barriers are required. In addition, in the field of innovation policy, the network-based policy approach focuses on the network context rather than the spatial context, as well as strengthening the existing links between firms, institutions and other entities, building cross-sectoral networks, synergy, diversification and emerging knowledge exchange.

Summary. A sectoral systems approach in tourism emphasizes the sharing of industry-specific expertise and relevant knowledge between different sub-sectors along the value chain. Recently, European development and cohesion policy has been reformed and informed by these changes in contemporary thinking, resulting in a smart specialization agenda. Smart specialization refers to smart or specialized diversification around identified relevant activity topics aimed at identifying new opportunities.

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